

COMPARISON OF GENETIC ALGORITHM AND ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK FOR DAMAGE DETECTION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Zhongqing Su^{1,2}, Hang-Yin Ling¹, Li-Min Zhou¹, Kin-Tak Lau¹ & Lin Ye²

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering,
The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong SAR*

²*Laboratory of Smart Materials & Structures (LSMS)
Centre for Advanced Materials Technology (CAMT)
School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Mechatronic Engineering
The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia*

SUMMARY: Comparison of genetic algorithm (GA) and artificial neural network (ANN) for quantitative assessment of delamination in composite laminates was conducted. For this purpose, a theoretical model was established to relate the delamination parameters with the alteration in structural frequency response functions (FRFs). Based on the model, an objective function was designed, and minimising such a function using GA led to the determination of delamination parameters; meanwhile a BP-feedforward ANN was developed and trained using the eigenvalues extracted from FRFs. For validation, glass fibre-reinforced composite (GFRP) beams containing various delaminations were examined and eigenvalues were obtained from measurement by embedded fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. Both algorithms were then collated in terms of identification precision and computational cost.

KEYWORDS: genetic algorithm (GA), artificial neural network (ANN), fibre Bragg grating (FBG), damage detection

INTRODUCTION

Quantitative damage assessment of composite structures is known as a problem of *inverse* pattern recognition. Both in the category of artificial intelligence (AI), genetic algorithm (GA) and artificial neural network (ANN) are two effective approaches towards this issue. In brief, GA is based on a stochastic and highly adaptive search and optimisation originated from the principia of natural selection and genetic evolution [1], while ANN operates as a parallel computational model to authentically explore the connection between a series of reasons (*inputs*) and consequences (*outputs*) for a system [2]. Damage identification techniques based on GA [3-5] and ANN [6-8] have been well developed in the past one decade, some being particularly tailored for composite structures [9-10].

With different theoretical bases, GA and ANN can present their unique advantages and disadvantages for damage recognition. In the present study, both algorithms were comparatively characterised by quantitative assessment of delamination in glass fibre-reinforced composite (CFRC) laminates. A theoretical model and an objective function were

developed in virtue of shift in structural eigenvalues. And to minimise the function using GA led to the identification of delamination. Meanwhile, a feedforward ANN was constructed and trained using eigenvalues obtained from the theoretical model for the delaminated beam. Experimental validation was conducted through identifying actual delamination in GFRC beams, where the eigenvalues were extracted from the measurement by embedded fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors.

PRINCIPLES OF GA AND ANN

Genetic Algorithm

With a global optimum configuration and strong robustness, a genetic algorithm (GA) is able to deal with most of the recognition problems with or without constraints, by using multiple points from a population of points in region of the whole possible solution space [4]. An objective function is customised first to describe a physical problem, and minimising the function leads to the determination of engaged parameters. A typical GA includes five major operations in order: *encoding*, *evaluation*, *selection*, *crossover* and *mutation* [11]. In this procedure, a GA is firstly initialised with a randomly generated number set, named *population*. Each individual in the population is known as a *chromosome*. Subsequently, GA evaluates the chromosomes based on the objective function and calculates the fitness for each individual, and the individuals with higher fitness have more chance to be selected to produce the offspring. The next generation of the chromosomes is created using genetic operators, crossover and mutation. When the pre-defined number of generations or convergence criteria is met, the GA is automatically terminated and an optimal solution is finally achieved.

Artificial Neural Network

Developed on psychology, statistics and neurophysiology, an artificial neural network (ANN) emulates the human brain mechanisms, capable of deducing consequences for an unknown stimulus according to the pre-accumulated knowledge or information, while it evades interrogating the intricate constitutive relationship. Early studies indicate that any continuous system can be well described by an error-backpropagation (BP) ANN [2]. Following this, a BP-ANN was created in this study, and the scaled conjugate gradient (SCG)-based supervised learning [2] was adopted. During ANN training, the weights and biases were iteratively upgraded and optimised along the negative gradient, by comparing the actual network outputs with the expected targets. A *mean square error* (MSE) was introduced to monitor the network convergence, defined as

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [t(i) - o(i)]^2 \quad (1)$$

where $t(i)$ and $o(i)$ are the target and output vectors for every iteration, respectively. N denotes the number of elements in the target vector.

GA- AND ANN-BASED IDENTIFICATION

Structural Model

A structural beam, with dual fixed ends, containing a through-width delamination was considered, as shown in Fig. 1. All the dimensional features are illustrated on the figure. Three parameters were used to describe the delamination: location of a , span of b and

interlaminar position of d_2 . Such a beam model was simplified using four segments, and each of them was treated as an isotropic Euler beam [12], referring to Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Theoretical model of structural beam containing delamination

The transverse governing equations for 4 segments are defined in a dimensionless form as

$$\frac{\partial^4 \bar{w}_i}{\partial \bar{x}_i^4} + \left(\frac{\rho A L^4}{EI} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_i}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad \text{for segments 1 and 4} \quad (2a)$$

$$-EI_2 \frac{\partial^4 \bar{w}_2}{\partial \bar{x}_2^4} - P_d \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_2}{\partial \bar{x}_2^2} - \rho A_2 \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_2}{\partial t^2} - p = 0, \quad \text{for segment 2} \quad (2b)$$

$$-EI_3 \frac{\partial^4 \bar{w}_3}{\partial \bar{x}_3^4} + P_d \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_3}{\partial \bar{x}_3^2} - \rho A_3 \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}_3}{\partial t^2} + p = 0, \quad \text{for segment 3} \quad (2c)$$

where E , ρ , A_i , I_i , $\bar{x}_i = x_i/L$ and $\bar{w}_i = w_i/d$ ($i=1, 2, 3, 4$), are the elastic modulus, density, cross-section area, second moment of area, dimensionless axial coordinate and transverse displacement for the i^{th} segment, respectively; while p is the density of normal contact pressure on delamination surfaces between the two segments and P_d denotes the magnitude of an axial load in each segment. Applied with the continuum conditions and without consideration of non-linear terms [12], w_2 is forced to be equal to w_3 , as well as x_2 to x_3 , everywhere in the delaminated region. Further, to unify Eqns. 2a-2c can lead to

$$\bar{w}_i(\bar{x}_i) = F_i C_i \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
F_i &= [f_{1i}(\bar{x}_i) \quad f_{2i}(\bar{x}_i) \quad f_{3i}(\bar{x}_i) \quad f_{4i}(\bar{x}_i)] \\
f_{1i}(x_i) &= \sin(\lambda_i \bar{x}_i), \quad f_{2i}(x_i) = \cos(\lambda_i \bar{x}_i), \\
f_{3i}(x_i) &= \sinh(\lambda_i \bar{x}_i), \quad f_{4i}(x_i) = \cosh(\lambda_i \bar{x}_i)
\end{aligned}$$

and C_i ($C_i = [c_{1i} \quad c_{2i} \quad c_{3i} \quad c_{4i}]^T$) is a constant matrix. λ_i is the eigenvalue of structural beam [12], given by

$$\lambda_1^4 = \lambda_4^4 = \lambda^4 = \frac{\rho A \omega^2 L^4}{EI}, \quad \lambda_2^4 = \lambda_3^4 = \frac{\rho(A_2 + A_3)\omega^2 L^4}{E(I_2 + I_3)} = \frac{\lambda^4}{(\bar{d}_2^3 + \bar{d}_3^3)} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{d}_2 = d_2/d$ and $\bar{d}_3 = d_3/d$. Meanwhile, the structural natural frequency, δ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3 \dots$) can be further obtained by

$$\delta_i = \frac{\lambda_i^2}{2\pi L^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho}} \quad (5)$$

GA-based Identification

An objective function, J , was designed in terms of the first three eigenvalues of the beam as

$$J(a, b, d_2) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{(\lambda_{m0}^i - \lambda_m^i) - (\lambda_{t0}^i - \lambda_t^i)}{\lambda_{m0}^i} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

where λ_m^i and λ_{m0}^i are the eigenvalues at the i^{th} vibration mode of the beams with/without a delamination measured by the sensors, respectively. Similarly, λ_t^i and λ_{t0}^i are the eigenvalues at the i^{th} vibration mode of the beams with/without a delamination calculated from the beam model, respectively.

Applying GA, the fittest delamination parameters (a , b , and d_2 of the delamination) can be determined by minimising Eqn. (6), which was fulfilled by an in-house program. 40 populations and 10 genes were chosen in each chromosome. Representatively, a convergence curve is displayed in Fig. 2. It is obvious that the objective function converges with no more than 50 generations.

ANN-based Identification

A feedforward BP-ANN was constructed, featured by one single processing neural layer, one input layer with 3 values (first three eigenvalues of the beam) and one output layer with 3 variables (a , b and d_2). A *log-sigmoid*, defined as $T(\Omega) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\Omega}}$, was used to connect the input layer with the processing layer. All the variables in ANN were preliminarily normalised, limited in the range of [0, 1].

Fig. 2: Convergence of objective function

100 through-width delaminations were randomly chosen to individually occur in the beam along the beam axis, where $0 \leq a \leq 0.7$, $0 \leq b \leq 0.5$, meantime $0 \leq a + b \leq 1$, $0 < d_2 < 1$ (0.1, 0.2, ..., 0.8, 0.9 only). First three order eigenvalues for each damage case were obtained in virtue of the theoretical model as the ANN input, while the corresponding three delamination parameters were adopted as the training target. The training progress is displayed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Convergence of ANN training

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To calibrate GA- and ANN-based damage identification approaches, experimental validation was conducted. 5 GFRC beams ($E_{11} = E_{22} = 13.36 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = 5.84 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.14$ and $\rho = 1664.03 \text{ kg/m}^3$), shaped at $440 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$, were fabricated using balanced plain weave fabric at a stacking sequence of $[0^\circ]_{10}$, and 4 of them were introduced with a delamination by inserting Telfon[®] film between layers during manufacturing, while one keep intact as the benchmark, denoted by *SP1-SP4* and *SP0*, respectively.

Fibre Bragg gratings (FBGs) (wavelength λ_B : $1540.044nm$ and sensor length: $10mm$) were embedded into GF/EP specimens between the 1st and 2nd laminae during fabrication, whose centre was located $120mm$ away from the right beam end, to collect the structural dynamic responses. The experiment setup is displayed in Fig. 4. The beam was excited by an electric-driven shaker with an amplified random signal, and responses were monitored by a FBG dynamic strain measurement system [9] and then uploaded to the signal analyser to get the frequency response functions (FRFs).

Fig. 4: Experimental setup

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FRFs of all the specimens were obtained from the analyser. The first natural frequencies were extracted from FRFs to obtain the eigenvalues in terms of Eqn. 5, compared with those from the theoretical model in Table 1.

Table 1: Natural frequencies from experimental measurement and theoretical model

Specimen	Mode Order	By Experiment	By Theoretical Model	Err. [abs%]
SP0	1	4.45	4.73	5.92
	2	7.49	7.85	4.59
	3	10.80	10.99	1.73
SP1	1	4.17	4.45	6.29
	2	6.93	7.28	4.81
	3	10.31	10.51	1.90
SP2	1	4.44	4.73	6.13
	2	7.26	7.64	4.97
	3	10.78	10.92	1.28
SP3	1	4.41	4.72	6.57
	2	6.16	7.24	14.92
	3	9.50	10.73	11.46
SP4	1	4.38	4.67	6.21
	2	6.59	6.63	0.60
	3	9.73	9.67	0.62

The evolution of prediction for 3 damage parameters against the GA generation by using the designed objective function is illustrated in Figs. 5, respectively for *SP1-SP4*. Meanwhile, the predicted damage parameters from both GA- and ANN-based approaches are collated with the actual values in Table 2.

Fig. 5: Progress of prediction for delamination parameters against GA generation for (a) *SP1*; (b) *SP2*; (c) *SP3*; (d) *SP4*

Table 2: Comparison of GA- and ANN-based identification

Specimen No.	Real Value	By GA	Err. [abs%]	By ANN-1	Err. [abs%]	
SP1	<i>a</i>	0.05	0.037	25.8	0.054	8.1
	<i>b</i>	0.25	0.251	0.5	0.238	4.8
	d_2	0.50	0.576	15.2	0.508	1.6
SP2	<i>a</i>	0.375	0.382	1.9	0.336	10.4
	<i>b</i>	0.25	0.233	6.9	0.237	5.2
	d_2	0.20	0.224	12	0.219	9.5
SP3	<i>a</i>	0.375	0.378	0.9	0.387	3.2
	<i>b</i>	0.25	0.279	11.4	0.261	4.4
	d_2	0.50	0.633	26.5	0.464	7.2
SP4	<i>a</i>	0.30	0.278	7.5	0.287	4.3
	<i>b</i>	0.40	0.399	0.3	0.437	9.3
	d_2	0.50	0.503	0.7	0.464	7.2

A more even distribution of prediction error is noticed for the ANN-based approach compared with the GA-based one, where the largest error reaches 26% for predicting interlaminar position in *SP3*. In general, for predicting an individual damage parameter, both two algorithms perform well with no obvious advantage for either of them. For the recognition using ANN, the precision is subjected to the training data, and for those damages which are in the range involving more assumed damage patterns during training, the prediction is usually more precise. While the precision of GA-based approach is highly dependent on the encoding methods, number of individuals and genetic operators. An optimal number of individuals and genetic operators could be helpful in obtaining more precise results within a certain number of generations [11].

Approximately 15 minutes was consumed to reach the convergence for the designed objective functions using GA, while such a cost for ANN training is below 5 minutes by using SCG-based backpropagation (Pentium® M 1.70GHZ, 1G DDR RAM). Nevertheless, if considering the whole cost, including data preparation for network training, the ANN-based method is quite time and effort-consuming. Contrarily, GA does not need a large amount of user-provided patterns for the function minimisation. For such an application in one-dimensional beam structure, in which a theoretical model can be easily established to relate damage parameters with change in structural response, GA can be an effective solution. However, applications to complicated structures where an appropriate objective function can not easily be formulated might be problematic.

CONCLUSION

Efficiency of genetic algorithm (GA) and artificial neural network (ANN) for quantitative evaluation of delamination in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy composite beams was evaluated. Considering both the prediction precision and computational cost, both algorithms are able to offer satisfactory evaluation on delamination location, size and interlaminar position, while ANN seems performs more steadily with better precision in general; however more efforts have been consumed for preparation of ANN training patterns. For those complicated structures, where theoretical model and objective function can hardly be established, ANN seems more versatile than GA. The results have also demonstrated the excellent performance of FBG in authentically collecting the dynamic response of composite structures.

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